

Impact of State Honour' Initiative: Tamil Nadu Registers All-time Increase in Organ Donations

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Tamil Nadu has set a new record and has reported 268 deceased organ donations in 2024, against 178 in 2023, leading to 1,500 deceased donor organ transplants in a year. The state retrieved 863 solid organs and 637 tissues, the highest numbers since the inception of state's deceased donor transplant program in 2008.

The increase has been attributed to the Tamil Nadu government's State Honour initiative, introduced in September 2023, to honour deceased organ donors at their funerals. 326 of them have received State Honours; inspiring a total of 11,547 voluntary new registrations in 2024, bringing the total to 19,097 in just 2 years.

By offering continuous medical education programs and supporting grief-stricken families, the Tamil Nadu Transplant Authority (TRANSTAN) has helped in achieving this rise, said Dr N Gopalakrishnan, Member-Secretary, TRANSTAN. He also added, that the "Honour Walk," first initiated by the Rajiv Gandhi Government General Hospital (RGGGH) in Chennai, and currently carried out by several other government medical facilities is responsible for the rise in numbers. This is also one of the factors motivating many individuals to donate their organs.

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